

Where do Germany's electricity imports come from?

A tale of energy system data availability and interpretation

Mirko Schäfer¹

¹Albert-Ludwigs-Universität Freiburg, Germany

Abstract:

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1 Introduction

In 2023, Germany experienced a reversal in its electricity trade balance, shifting from its long-standing position as a net exporter to becoming a net importer of electricity for the first time since 2003. This development has been commented on broadly in the public debate. A key point of discussion has been the perception that Germany's electricity system has become dependent on foreign generation. Additionally, questions have arisen regarding the origin of imported electricity, including its supplier countries and generation sources.

The origin of imported electricity often is analyzed based on close to real-time data from Transmission System Operators, including market results, physical and scheduled commercial flows, generation and load data [1], [2]. Nevertheless, the interpretation of this data, the methods applied to determine the origin of imports, and the conclusions drawn from the results are far from being straightforward. The widely used scheduled commercial flows published by the European Network of Transmission System Operators (ENTSO-E), for instance, are often misinterpreted in the context of import/export relations. These flows do not necessarily represent direct bilateral trades between neighboring countries but are algorithmically derived for scheduling, market coordination, or analytical purposes. Given the nature of Europe's coupled electricity market, the concept of the origin of electricity imports thus depends on the interpretation of the data, and the method applied to derive corresponding results.

2 Methods

This contribution reviews the data sources and the various methodological approaches to determine the origin of electricity imported into Germany, utilizing hourly power system data from ENTSO-E for the period 2021 to 2024. The different methods are based on *scheduled commercial flows*, *zonal net positions*, and a *flow tracing* approach. While scheduled commercial flows are often used to determine import/export relations, they are ex-post algorithmic calculations and do not represent explicit bilateral trades. Nevertheless, we reproduce results based on this approach as a benchmark for alternative methods and interpretations.

In the European coupled day-ahead electricity market, net imports and exports for each zone are determined by optimizing trade relationships under transmission constraints to maximize overall welfare [3]. Accordingly, hourly zonal net positions provide a more economically meaningful perspective on import/export relationships. From a physical perspective, flow tracing methods represent a heuristic approach to determine

the origin of imports based on power flow patterns in the transmission system. The application of such a method thus provides a more intuitive view of the origins of imported electricity based on zonal net positions and physical flows [4], [5].

Each method involves specific assumptions and methodological choices that influence the resulting interpretation of the "origin" of imported electricity.

3 Results and conclusion

Our analysis of the ENTSO-E data illustrates that the concept of the "origin of imported electricity" does not have a unique and literal economic representation in the framework of European electricity market coupling. Rather, for the available close to real-time data, any analysis of this topic has to clarify the underlying interpretation, data and applied methods.

Author contributions

Conceptualization, M.S., A.W. .; methodology, M.S., T.B. writing—original draft preparation, M.S.; writing—review and editing, M.S., T.B., A.W.; supervision, A.W.

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Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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